

USAGE OF AUDIO-LINGUAL METHOD FOR IMPROVING LEARNERS VOCABULARY

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Abstract: The audio-lingual method became a popular approach to foreign language teaching in the mid-20th century and still plays an important role in many classes. In a departure from earlier methods based on reading and writing, audio-lingual instruction emphasizes spoken language with correct pronunciation and grammar. Audio-lingual theory sees language learning as habit formation, so audio-lingual activities primarily use repetition and drill to teach students correct forms in the new tongue. Because of the emphasis on natural spoken language, the audio-lingual method presents grammar and vocabulary through dialogues. Each dialogue also has a cultural context, such as shopping for clothing. The teacher first reads each line of the dialogue or presents it with a recording. In chorus, students repeat each line of the dialogue after it's presented, eventually memorizing it through many repetitions. The teacher then takes one role and the class takes the other, and they also change parts. As additional activities, a small group or an individual student may role play the dialogue with the teacher. As a finale, pairs of students practice the dialogue together and present it to the class.

Key words: knowledge, method, instructional design, speaking skills, target language, EFL

Аннотация: Аудио-язычный метод стал популярным подходом к преподаванию иностранного языка в середине 20-го века и до сих пор играет важную роль во многих классах. В отличие от более ранних методов, основанных на чтении и письме, аудио-языковая инструкция подчеркивает разговорную язык с правильным произношением и грамматикой. Аудио-лингвистическая теория видит изучение языка как формирование привычек, поэтому аудио-лингвистические действия в первую очередь используют повторение и дрил, чтобы преподавать правильные формы студентов на новом языке. Из-за акцента на естественном разговорном языке, аудио-язычный метод представляет грамматику и словарный запас через диалоги. Каждый диалог также имеет культурный контекст, такой как покупки для одежды. Учитель сначала читает каждую строку диалога или представляет его с записью. В

При пении студенти повторяют каждую линию диалога после ее представления, в конечном итоге запоминают его через много повторений. Затем учитель принимает одну роль, и класс принимает другой, и они также меняют детали. В качестве дополнительных мероприятий небольшая группа или отдельный студент, могут роли играть на диалог с учителем. Как финал, пары студентов практикуют диалог вместе и представляют его классу.

Ключевые слова: знания, метод, инструкция дизайн, разговорные навыки, целевой язык, EFL

Annotatsiya: Audio-til metodi 20-asr o'rtalarida chet tilini o'rgatishda mashhur yondashuvga aylandi va hozirgacha ko'plab sinflarda muhim rol o'ynamoqda. O'qish va yozishga asoslangan oldingi usullardan voz kechish, audio-til o'rgatish to'g'ri talaffuz va grammatika bilan og'zaki tilga urg'u beradi. Audioratsion nazariya til o'rganishni odat shakllanishi sifatida ko'radi, shuning uchun audioratsion faoliyat birinchi navbatda o'quvchilarga yangi tilda to'g'ri shakllarni o'rgatish uchun takrorlash va mashqdan foydalanadi. Tabiiy og'zaki nutqqa e'tibor berilganligi sababli, audio-til usuli dialoglar orqali grammatika va lug'at bilan tanishtiradi. Har bir suhbatda kiyim-kechak xarid qilish kabi madaniy kontekst ham mavjud. O'qituvchi avval dialogning har bir satrini o'qiydi yoki uni eslatma bilan taqdim etadi. Pripeniyada talabalar dialogning har bir satrini taqdim etilgandan keyin takrorlaydilar va oxir-oqibat uni ko'p takrorlashlardan keyin yodlashadi. Keyin o'qituvchi bir rolni oladi va sinf boshqa rolni oladi va ular ham tafsilotlarni o'zgartiradilar. Qo'shimcha mashg'ulot sifatida kichik guruh yoki individual o'quvchi o'qituvchi bilan suhbatda rol o'ynashi mumkin. Yakuniy bosqich sifatida juftlik talabalar birgalikda dialogni mashq qiladilar va uni sinfga

Kalit so'zlar: bilim, usul, yo'riqnoma dizayni, so'zlashuv ko'nikmalari, maqsadli til, EFL

Introduction: Teaching profession is a challenging profession because teachers should possess a number of requirements such as pedagogical knowledge, subject matter knowledge, organization and communication skills, and socio-affective skills. In addition, teachers should know the varieties of language teaching methods, be flexible and creative, so they can attract their students 'attention in their instructional design (Saepullah, et al., 2021; Herawati, 2012). Since English is a global language, everyone uses it to communicate with others and it is essential for educational growth (Harmer, 2003; Haycraft, 2002). In Indonesia, for instance, English is not only taught at the higher level of education

but also the secondary level. Therefore, Indonesian EFL learners are urged to master the four English language skills, namely speaking, reading, listening, and writing. Speaking is the ability to produce oral output that consists of creating organized verbal utterances to express meaning (Nunan, 2003; Nazara, 2011). Furthermore, when we speak, we generate text, and that text should be meaningful (Derewianka, 1990). Brown, (2004) confirms that speaking is considered as the most important skills to be learned. Based on the four language skills, the system may be divided into two categories; spoken and written abilities (Mart, 2018; Nunan, 2003; Richards and Rodgers, 1986). Teachers should possess knowledge of different method of language teaching and be flexible in their instructional design. Indeed, it is hard to pict out one best single method for all due to the learners' age, language level, and the materials being taught. Most teachers combine their teaching methods to facilitae their learning and teaching. Therefore, teachers should be flexible in their instructional design, selecting and adapting them when needed. Several teaching methods may be applied to teach the four language skills, such as Direct Method, Audio Lingual Method, Communicative Language Learning, and Communicative Language Teaching. The use of a suitable teaching method is considered necessary when teaching English language skills. The appropriate use of a teaching method is one of the ways to enhance learners' speaking skills. However, teaching speaking is not an easy task because learners at the same time should comprehend several language components such as pronunciation, grammar, and vocabulary (Leong and Ahmadi, 2017). That is why an appropriate teaching method should be presented to ensure that EFL learners possess communication skills. Literature review showed that the Audio-Lingual Method (ALM) is one of the suitable teaching methods that may be applied to teach speaking skills because it ignites learners' willingness to communicate in the target language. It is in line with Freeman (2000), who states that learners could improve their speaking skills through the use of the ALM. Moreover, it helps EFL learners communicate in the target language and achieve communicative competence in a wide range of foreign languages. In its implementation, the ALM utilizes repetition, replacement, and question-answering to develop learners' speaking abilities, particularly their vocabulary. According to Richard and Rodgers (1986), language skills are learned more effectively if the items to be learned in the target language are presented in the spoken form before they are seen in written form.

Conclusion: The present study attempts to delineate the utilization of the ALM to enhance EFL learners' speaking skills. The reason why the ALM is because this particular teaching method is in line with the language learning objectives is to learn how to use the language to communicate (Freeman, 2000). Besides, it is widely used to train learners to communicate in a target language. The present study is worth conducting because it may shed some light on the effective teaching method used to enhance learners' speaking skills. Besides, it contributes to the existing body of knowledge, especially in Teaching English as a Foreign Language (TEFL), in terms of the knowledge of an appropriate teaching method which will be used by EFL teachers to suit the needs of EFL learners in the classroom setting. Bearing in mind the importance of the aforementioned issues, this article reviews the brief of the ALM and its the purposes. Furthermore, it scrutinizes the strategies used in the ALM, the benefits, and the implication of using the ALM in classroom teaching. Several important points on the use of ALM are highlighted in the conclusion part as the final remarks.

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